

REPRESENTATION OF THE CATEGORY OF ASPECT IN RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article is devoted to a brief review of the category of Aspect in Russian and English. The author considers the form, based on the meaning of the achieved limit, as the top of the expression of aspectual relations in the language. the top of the expression of aspectual relations in the language.

Keywords: aspect, imperfect, perfect, russian verb, english verb

The comparison of the two languages goes back to ancient times. However, its scientific study began comparatively recently - at the end of the 19th century. The question of comparison is central to the theory of language interaction[1].

The development of the grammatical structure of language comes from the growing needs of people for mutual understanding, as grammatical tools serve as a means of exchange and agreement in thoughts.

The laws of language development are objective in nature, changes in the grammatical structure of language are caused by the objective needs of communication and mutual understanding. The latter are constantly growing with the development of production and economy, science and technology, politics and culture, social life and everyday life. The language constantly brings its grammatical means in accordance with the needs of mutual understanding between people.

In Russian, verbs are of two kinds: imperfect (read, sit down, get up, etc.) and perfect (read, sit down, get up). Due to the synthetic nature of the Russian language, the perfect/imperfect form of a verb is its permanent feature. For example: the verbs

видеть - увидеть are two separate verbs, not two forms of the same verb to see. Thus, the category of form in Russian is not part of the system of verb tenses, which means that the system of verb tenses in Russian is purely temporal.

In English, the words see - вижу and have seen - увидел are forms of the same verb to see, and the system of verb modification is species-temporal. Moreover, the English verb can appear not in two kinds (perfect/ imperfect), but in four: the Indefinite, or Simple, or Common Aspect, the Perfect Aspect, the Continuous Aspect, and the Perfect Continuous Aspect.

The meaning of the perfect form of an English verb generally coincides with the meaning of perfect verbs in Russian:

I have read this book. - Я уже прочел эту книгу.

The long form of the verb in English reflects the action in its development at a certain moment or period of time. In Russian, this meaning of momentary action is conveyed either by the verb itself, by the circumstances of the time, or by the context:

Where are you going? – Куда ты идешь? (but not «ходишь»)

What are you doing now? – Что ты сейчас делаешь? (adverbial modifier of time)

Take the kettle off the stove, the water is boiling. – С ними чайник с плиты, вода кипит (context).

An English verb can combine two kinds (perfect and continuous) at the same time. Such a mixed verb form is called a Perfect Continuous and denotes an action that has continued for some period of time before the present moment and possibly continues afterwards. For example:

I have been waiting for you for two hours. – Я жду тебя уже 2 часа.

The firemen have been trying to put out a big forest fire in California. – Пожарные пытаются погасить большой лесной пожар в Калифорнии [3].

In teaching practice, the grammatical semantics of the verb form is often defined through the notion of «finality / incompleteness of action». A. V. Isachenko wrote: «The notion of «finality» also blurs the line between temporal and purely species

semantic elements: after all, we can speak of «finality» only in relation to past tense forms (perfect form) of the type he said, he wrote» [2, p. 134]. Such perfect verbs as *застучать, поползти* and others do not indicate finality. Future perfect forms such as *прочитаем, запишем, открою* and others express action that has not yet been performed, which contradicts the notion of finality. However, imperfect past tense verbs can express the finality of an action: «*рассказывал, приезжал, подписывал*» and others. Therefore, when studying verb types, it is not recommended to use the terms «finality / incompleteness of action». It is more appropriate in most cases to use the term «performance» for the perfect form and «non-performance» for the imperfect form.

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